

Factors Affecting the Work Efficiency of Employees of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

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Abstract—The objectives of this project are to study on the work efficiency of the employees, sorted by their profiles, and to study on the relation between job attributes and work efficiency of employees of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The samples used for this study are 292 employees. The statistics used in this study are frequencies, standard deviations, One-way ANOVA and Pearson's correlation coefficient. Majority of respondent were male with an undergraduate degree, married and lives together. The average age of respondents was between 31-41 years old, married and the educational background are higher than bachelor's degree. The job attribute is correlated to the work efficiency with the statistical significance level of .01. This concurs with the predetermined hypothesis. The correlation between the two main factors is in the moderate level. All the categories of job attributes such as the variety of skills, job clarity, job importance, freedom to do work are considered separately.

Keywords—Employees, Job Attributes, Work Efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN addition to focusing on the management and technology, many organizations have turned their attention to improving organizational performance significantly. Organizations need access to the globalization for globalization has the potential to help improve employment outcomes. In order for this to be successful, it needs to improve three operational aspects: quality of work, speed and innovation, including the ability to bring a product or service in the market. [1]

Management model, improved performance of people, form of action or similar concepts of Frederick Taylor to succeed is some Japanese styles of management. The organization must be dedicated to the development of the operational system that will allow personnel to work well. More powerful new development will be aligned to the extensive development of the whole person, both working as a team and the quality of work life. Lifetime employment system in Japan is a system that works effectively which results the personnel to be more dedicated and doing their best by working hard. Japanese management that is difficult to imitate by someone is to have systems and procedures in the administration which allow people to engage in creative thinking, proposing and participating in the work. [4] This idea is effective to the extent that can it be done using the system administration QC Circles, that facilitates the life and work greatly, makes the

working environment better, comfortable, safe and proud to work to. [2]

To make available personnel works for the organization efficiently; it needs to build a commitment and willingness to learn. When personnel became attached to his work, he will perform his job with a sense of responsibility, commitment, and pride for his work and most important; strive to be the best employee that a company has ever seen. These will make him successful in any kind of work. But sometimes organizational commitments affect organizational performance due to some factors like management decisions. The management should set a unique and understandable concept of their own goal. Personnel working with a sense of commitment and are willing to put his effort in working will also benefit the organization and he will achieved his goal [3]. Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University is a university with a specialization on information services (Information Management) and has complete system (Turnkey System) consulting services. This also designs and develops services including hardware and software equipment related to the institution. Banking and Financial Institutions meet the needs of customers ranging from governments to private enterprises; therefore, it is reasonable to have a distribution site to provide better service to customers. Sometimes the operation or coordination within organizations is not effective in practice. The job characteristics, depictions of participation in decision-making and staff within the organization have no ties to the organization and leads to inefficiency in the work performance. It is necessary to have empowering employees within the organization and working together effectively will ensure the quality of performance. [3]

For this reason, researchers are interested to study the factors that affect the work efficiency of employees at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The nature of job, commitment to the organization and staff members' operational effectiveness is examined. The findings from this study will benefit the administration of the university, as well as other relevant personnel, who was hired for setting the personnel management guidelines of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University that will maximize the work efficiency of its employees and that will lead to success.

II. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this research was to study work efficiency of employees of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University and relation between job nature and operational effectiveness and the data was employees of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University who already work in the Management Science

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faculty. [5] A total of 292 respondents were selected by using purposive sampling and collect by the questionnaire using ideas from Taro Yamane and analyze the data by the statistics used in this study are frequencies, standard deviations, One-way ANOVA and Pearson's correlation coefficient follow by this conceptual framework.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

III. FINDING

Employees with different genders, marital statuses, education levels, positions and years of experiences have similar operational effectiveness. However, employees with different ages have different factors that affect their work efficiency at a statistical significance level of .01. After the pair analysis, it is discovered that employees whose age range from 30-22 years have work efficiency level that is lower than that of the staff members whose ages fall from the range of 48-40 years.[6]

TABLE I
 EMPLOYEES DEMOGRAPHIC DESCRIPTIVE

Employees Demographic	Mean	Interpretation
1. - Gender	3.64	Effective
2. - Age	3.67	Effective
3. - Marital Status	3.74	Effective
4. - Education	3.64	Effective
5. - Position	3.27	Effective
6. - Years of Experience	3.34	Effective
Overall Mean	3.64	Effective

The overall job nature is significantly correlated to the work efficiency of employees with the statistical significance level of .01. This correlation is in the moderate level. Considered separately, the aspects of the diversity of skills, the job nature clarity, the importance of the job, the authority for decision-making and the job feedback are found to be correlated with each other with the statistical significance level of .01. Their correlations are in the moderate level. [7]

IV. DISCUSSION

The comparison of factors affecting the work efficiency of employees with different genders, ages, marital statuses, educations, positions and years of experiences leads to the

discovery that staff members with different ages and marital statuses have different levels of operational effectiveness. These findings concur with the findings from the study of who studied on the work efficiency of employees of the government which includes: communication division, the Office of the Permanent Secretary and Ministry of Interior. This study has used 80 samples and used frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations and correlation coefficients in testing the research hypotheses. The findings from the study revealed that most of the officials have the moderate level of work efficiency. The officials with different marital statuses, genders, ages and educations have different levels of work efficiency which affects them. The factors that influence their work efficiency are the clarity of their job nature and the importance of the job, which are correlated to the work efficiency of employees.

The findings from the study also concur with the findings from the study of [6] who studied on the job nature that are correlated to the motivation to build up the work efficiency of employees of 28 Kilometers Engineering Co., Ltd., and discovered that the job nature and the motivations of the employees are correlated to each other in the positive direction and the high level [7].

V. SUGGESTIONS

1. The organization should encourage senior staff members to share their job related knowledge to new ones through several activities such as holding an event in which employees can share their work experiences. This will develop knowledge and skills and boost employees' experiences that can be applied to the operations in order to increase the operational effectiveness.
2. The organization should also set its career advancement direction that emphasizes on personnel development by allowing all staff members to know how to have career opportunities and advancements so that they will know how they can be promoted or rotated to other jobs, and what welfare or remunerations they will receive from a particular job. This is because the findings from the study reveal that career advancement is correlated to the factors that affect employees' work efficiency in the low level.
3. The motivation to work is found to be moderately correlated to the operational effectiveness. Hence, the organization should have the policy to respond to its employees' need to express their satisfaction toward their jobs so that they will have the eagerness and commitment to work and to help the organization accomplish its objectives. This means the organization should encourage its staff members to attend seminars or training workshops in order to obtain updated knowledge or experiences that can be applied to their jobs.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE STUDIES

1. There should be a study on the factors that are correlated to the employees' commitment to Suan Sunandha

University because there no academic study which has been made for this matter.

2. There should be additional studies on the factors that affect employees' work motivation, morale, satisfaction and effectiveness in the in-depth manner by studying on factors other than those studied in this study. This will lead to the attainment of additional knowledge that can be used for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the staff members.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank Assoc. Prof. Dr. Luedech Girdwichai, President of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand for the financial support. The author would also like to thank Asst. Prof. Dr. Prateep Wajeethongratana, Dean of Faculty of Management Science for the full support on this research.

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